

Marilena Vlad, *Damascius et l'ineffable: récit de l'impossible discours*, Vrin, Paris, 2019; ISBN: 978-2-7116-2873-5

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In Plato's *Timaeus*, we are told that “to find the maker and father of the All (τὸ πᾶν) is laborious, and assuming [the maker] is found, to declare him to all is impossible (εἰς πάντα ἀδύνατον λέγειν)” (28c3–5). So it may come as a surprise that, at the end of the Neoplatonic Academy's era in Athens, this declaration takes on an ironically newfound meaning when Damascius (c. 462–post-532 CE) declares the first principle of the All (or “all things”, τὰ πάντα) to be entirely unspeakable and unthinkable—what Damascius calls the Ineffable (τὸ ἀπόρητον/ἄρρητον).

Damascius' claim is a sharp contrast to the preceding tradition, going back to Plotinus, which held the One to be the first principle. It is not as if previous Neoplatonists had no concept of ineffability for the First: they were well-known for claiming that the One transcends all being, such that nothing can be said of it—in other words ineffable. And yet this same principle is also treated as the identifiable first cause of all beings that come from it. As many have recognized,¹ there is a tension here: how can one and the same principle, which is completely transcendent and ineffable, function as a cause, which implies an immediate, immanent relation to the thing it causes—necessitating expression? Damascius exploits this tension with his notion of the Ineffable as the true first principle over the One and all things.

This background contextualizes Marilena Vlad's study on Damascius' Ineffable, which is mainly considered as the limit of thought, yet a limit which reveals the principle's presence. Vlad's book joins a growing number of recent works which touch on the Ineffable in Damascius, though till now there has been no monograph study dedicated just to the Ineffable. A recent parallel to Vlad's work is Damian Caluori's 2018 article, “*Aporia* and the Limits of Reason and of Language in Damascius”, where he argues that the *De Principiis*' first *aporia* (I.1–2)² is meant to open the horizon of thought to the first principle which cannot be thought or spoken. Vlad's book is effectively a thorough exploration of this general thesis, though somewhat unlike Caluori, she looks at the *aporia* as a sign, rather than the main step, for thought to begin looking for the Ineffable. Hence for Vlad, Damascius' main achievement lies in shifting the focus to considering the first principle of thought in itself, rather than of objective, external reality, as for previous Neoplatonists (p. 12). Overall Vlad's judgment seems right, though as I indicate below, this does not remove the fact that Damascius is also concerned with the objective problematic of causality,³ in addition to the difficulty of *thinking* about that problematic.

In the first chapter of the book's Part I, Vlad discusses the first, formal *aporia* in the *De Principiis*, where Damascius raises the question whether the principle is “before” or “together with” all things (τὰ

¹ Among others, see e.g. Steel (1999), esp. p. 364.

² Line numbers and pages from Westerink-Combès' edition.

³ Effectively the angle I address in my recent book, in Greig (2021), pp. 219–307.

πάντα). Vlad shrewdly notes that Damascius’ phrasing places more emphasis on the thinking subject which is conditioned by its conception of τὰ πάντα: for example, Damascius refers to the “so-called first principle of all things” (ἡ μία τῶν πάντων ἀρχὴ λεγομένη), reflecting that the *aporia*’s “principle” does not immediately correlate to the Ineffable or the One, but rather sets up the problematic for eventually finding the principle (pp. 24 ff.). Unlike Proclus’ *Platonic Theology*, which refers to the previous tradition on first principles, Damascius makes no mention of this: the *aporia*, like the *aporai* in the first half of Plato’s *Parmenides* (alongside, not mentioned by Vlad, those of Aristotle’s *Metaphysics B*), is a way of clearing the mind from all prior, problematic presuppositions and beginning anew (pp. 22–23). The impasse that results—when the principle is shown to be neither “with” nor “before” all things—does not indicate a failure of discursive thought, but rather a sign of another way to find the ultimate principle (pp. 32–33). This does not render discursive thought meaningless (against certain recent interpretations), but rather it becomes a concomitant part, and thus tool, of uncovering the true, uncoordinated principle.

Chapters 2 and 3 show the next steps from this impasse: in Ch. 2, detailing *DP* I.2.21–3.21, one potential way around the impasse is when Damascius classifies τὰ πάντα in three categories: as differentiated and plural (i.e. “all things” in itself); as plural, but without differentiation (i.e. the Unified); and as without differentiation and plurality (i.e. the One). Damascius’ latter classification with the One initially seems to solve the *aporia*’s impasse: it lacks the character of plurality and differentiation of τὰ πάντα (hence “before”), as Vlad notes, yet is still identified with τὰ πάντα, as containing them together (hence “with”). But when phrased in terms of its *coordination* (σύνταξις) with plurality, the impasse recurs, as Ch. 3 next shows. As Vlad emphasizes (pp. 56–59), this becomes a feature of thought that cannot be avoided (e.g. *DP* I.4.6–9): duality is imported into entities like the One that do not contain this feature in themselves. Still, thought’s ascent to the One, despite involving duality, implies something prior to this insurmountable duality. One is thus reminded of the need to ascend beyond the limiting nature of discursive thought, which is characterized by duality and within the bounds of totality (παντότης).

One general question I had throughout Part I is whether Damascius’ problematic is limited to human reasoning alone, or whether it also extends to the hierarchical level of intellect—despite Vlad’s claim in p. 32 that “all things” for Damascius are seen not from the view of divine intellect but rather the human soul. Vlad attributes Damascius’ problematic of “duality” to the soul’s discursivity, which does seem to be the operative context in the *De Principiis*. However Damascius’ description of τὰ πάντα itself—“all things” as existing in plurality and differentiation—fits the characterization of the divine intellect(s), which unfolds the plurality of the Forms as distinct from each other, in contrast to the principle of Being (i.e. the Unified) which contains the Forms without distinction. To my mind, Damascius’ problematic starts at the level of the human soul, but also extends to other principles like Intellect, which are not characterized by the soul’s discursivity but still imply the problematic of duality and differentiation.⁴ Vlad’s focus on human thinking makes sense, but this is one aspect where

⁴ A good example of this is Gertz (2016), on the relation between Being and Intellect—which Vlad cites but does not discuss.

I believe her analysis would be strengthened when also considering the greater problematic of procession in the Neoplatonic hierarchy of principles, as Damascius well exploits.⁵

I found Part III perhaps the most interesting in the book: Vlad discusses the “moyens para-discursifs” by which thought can attain to the Ineffable—particularly through “divining” (μαντεύεται) (Ch. 4), the “suppression” of discourse and passing into “nothingness” (τὸ οὐδέν) (Ch. 5), and “birth-laboring” (ὠδίζ) (Ch. 6). “Divining”, as Vlad shows, finds its roots in Plato, as describing truths which cannot be communicated straightforwardly by philosophical means (p. 68): for Damascius (loosely similar to Plato), it follows on the impasse of the *aporia*, pointing to something beyond itself. The act of “divining” only indicates that the principle is uncoordinated (ἀσύντακτον)—or rather incoordination *simpliciter* (p. 73). It is striking how, despite being a term directly related to theurgical contexts, Damascius seems to use the term in an agnostic, purely philosophical fashion: yet as Vlad insightfully notes, just as the ineffable symbols in theurgical acts connect the participant to the gods, so the act of “divining” connects the thinker with the Ineffable (p. 78). This goes together with the language of “birth-laboring” in the thinker’s attempt to attain the Ineffable, where identifying, locating, or speaking the Ineffable continually fails. Yet this is rather a sign of success, for Vlad: the continual process of laboring is, itself, constitutive of the act of accessing the Ineffable. In turn, the language of “nothingness” is another sign of the Ineffable, where, despite the term normally implying pure non-existence—“that which in no way is” (τὸ μηδαμῆ μηδαμῶς ὄν)—it also indicates a positive sense, as “nothing” above the One and all things. Hence “nothing” aptly describes the absolute sense of the Ineffable’s uncoordinated relation to τὰ πάντα.

One question that arises in discussing these “para-discursive” means is their relation to other, higher modes of knowledge. For Proclus and other late Neoplatonists, theurgy is constitutive of the highest kind of knowledge, because it directly links the participant to the principles of unity, instantiated in the gods (as henads), in contrast to knowing by intellection (νόησις, linked to Intellect) or discursive reasoning (διανόησις, linked to the soul). One wonders how this “para-discursive” method relates to theurgy for Damascius: would it not be a “higher” mode of knowing, even above theurgy, since it links to an even higher principle, i.e. the Ineffable? Vlad points to the well-known passage from Damascius’ *Commentary on Plato’s Phaedo* (I.172.1–5), where Damascius argues that Plato unifies the “hieratic school” prioritizing theurgy (i.e. Iamblichus, Proclus, etc.) with the “philosophical school” prioritizing intellection (i.e. Plotinus and Porphyry) (pp. 76–77). She uses this passage to argue that these “para-discursive means” symbolize this union, but one still wonders what this actually means in practice with the actual theurgical rites and their correlated mode of knowledge: does one continually employ this “birth-laboring” alongside the activity of knowing in theurgy? Or is there something else going on? One wishes Vlad would discuss this further, but perhaps the scope of the *De Principiis* (at least Volume I) limits these sorts of questions.

Finally, in Part III, Vlad focuses on the Ineffable itself, looking at the philosophical history of the term in Ch. 7, before turning to the notion of “overturning” (περιτροπή) in Ch. 8 as manifesting the Ineffable—more directly than in the “para-discursive” methods above—and in Ch. 9, Vlad shows how

⁵ A point emphasized in Butler (2013) and Butler (2019).

the Ineffable is found out all levels of reality for Damascius. In her historical survey, Vlad discusses precedents in Iamblichus and Proclus, as well as Plato and Damascius' interpretation of Plato. While Vlad overall gives a good, correct reading for Proclus and Iamblichus (from the latter's extant texts), it is somewhat puzzling that she does not also look at Damascius' own interpretations of the two Platonists in *DP* II.2–39: for instance, why does Damascius there seem to think that Iamblichus possesses the same notion of the Ineffable as his own—despite, as Vlad argues, the two conceptions being quite different? Furthermore, while she notes Proclus' adjectival use of the term, “ineffable” (ἄρρητον), for the “secret doctrines” of the Orphic texts and passages from Plato (pp. 135–136), Vlad surprisingly says nothing about *Platonic Theology* III.8, 32.8–15, where Proclus claims that the “very first, unitary god” (ὁ πρότιστος καὶ ἐνιαῖος θεός), implicitly the first principle, is “ineffable in itself, solely unitary, and beyond being” (κατ' αὐτὸ τὸ ἄρρητον καὶ ἐνιαῖον μόνον καὶ ὑπερούσιον).⁶ It is unfortunate that this passage is not mentioned, since Proclus' attribution of κατ' αὐτὸ τὸ ἄρρητον seems to imply ineffability as a defining characteristic in the same way as Damascius' substantival use of the term, “ineffable” (ἀπόρρητον), for the first principle. Ultimately, I concur with Vlad's “adjectival” reading for Proclus, including this text, but the context of *PT* III.8 is absolutely essential to bear in mind with Damascius' Ineffable.

In Ch. 8, Vlad outlines Damascius' various uses of “overturning” arguments and terms for the Ineffable, where they end up concluding with the opposite of their initial claims: for instance, to refer to the Ineffable is already a case of “overturning”, because we have just expressed what was claimed to be inexpressible. Vlad's overall claim is that these “overturning” arguments are not simply instances of linguistic self-contradiction, but rather directly signal “ce qui n'est plus de l'ordre de la pensée” (p. 145, n. 1). Despite the paradox, only this method is what ensures that the Ineffable is in no way determined, while simultaneously “demonstrating” its presence (p. 147)—what Vlad insightfully calls a kind of “ontological argument” (p. 165). Vlad discusses the Pyrrhonian Skeptical heritage of the method of περιτροπή (pp. 151 ff.), which is used in the Pyrrhonian's approach of neither dogmatically affirming nor denying claims concerning reality—i.e. the self-conscious use of terms and arguments implying their overturning in the context of judgments made about the nature of reality. As Vlad argues, Damascius is very similar in this approach, however applied to the Ineffable alone, not all reality as for the Skeptics.

Here I found Vlad's contrasting of the Skeptical approach against Damascius' somewhat misleading at times. For instance, she claims that the Pyrrhonian applies overturning only to the knowable, “imposing unknowability” on the knowable, while Damascius applies overturning to the unknowable as well as knowable (pp. 151–152). But one seems to find exactly this two-sided application in Sextus Empiricus, for instance when he acknowledges that the claim, “all things are false”, leads to its inversion, “not all things are false.”⁷ Furthermore, Vlad's characterization of the Skeptic's “suppression of thought” (e.g. p. 172) seems to defy Sextus' description of the Pyrrhonian who continually carries on

⁶ A passage that has been the source of controversy: see e.g. Gersh (2014), pp. 89–90, who claims that the “One” of the *Elements of Theology* only pertains to the Limit, rather than the first “One” of *PT* III.8.

⁷ Sextus Empiricus, *M* VIII.55; cf. VII.399. See Castagnoli (2010), pp. 114–120, and in general on self-refutation in the Pyrrhonian Skeptics, pp. 249–352.

investigating and searching for the truth.⁸ This also seems to match Vlad’s description of the perpetual openness that the engagement and experience of the Ineffable induces in “overturning” discourse, albeit for all of reality for the Pyrrhonian. Hence, I would rather modify the contrast perhaps in the following way: whereas the Skeptic has no orientation in reality in “overturning” discourse used for continually (and radically) investigating the reality behind the appearances, the Damascian student rather *has* an orientation: judgment is employed in the realm of “all things” (τὰ πάντα), but those judgments eventually lead to the highest principle which cannot involve any judgment. Hence this necessitates the radical method of overturning in appropriating that principle, i.e. the Ineffable.

Overall, I found Vlad’s book a dense but very insightful work on the different angles and aspects in which to reflect upon the Ineffable. It also raises a number of questions when putting Damascius’ work together with his commitment to the nature of objectively distinct—yet unified—gods/henads as primary principles: he does not seem to have given up Proclus’ framework in this regard, judging from skimming the final half of *DP* III. Putting this together with the subjective consideration of thought and its limits with the final principle proves to be a very rewarding experience—an experience beyond and within words.

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⁸ E.g. Sextus, *PHI*.3; cf. I.7.

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